

Deliverable 6.3.3.2

EXEMPLARY RESULTS OF SELF-HEALING REDISPATCH USING DISTRIBUTED
AUTONOMOUS AGENTS (RESEARCH DATA)

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Exemplary Results of Self-Healing Redispatch Using Distributed Autonomous Agents (Research Data)

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General Information

Summary

The integration of renewable energy resources into current energy systems requires well-coordinated interaction among grid components [1]. To efficiently manage high generation and grid congestion at all levels, intelligent neighborhood grids (energy communities) can be integrated into congestion management at higher grid levels [1] and participate in redispatch processes [2]. In such settings, distributed autonomous agents are considered for managing grid components [1], as they allow for self-organization and even self-healing [3]–[5]. To ensure a reliable supply, these distributed, agent-based optimization methods must be designed to be robust. The self-healing property of agent systems is necessary here to cope with disruptions and disturbances [5], [6].

The focus of this deliverable is research data, specifically exemplary results, with distributed autonomous agents in self-healing redispatch scenarios as the research subject. This deliverable emphasizes the overall research process to maximize the reusability of the intermediate steps, findings and final results. Additionally, the steps are discussed according to the phases of the research data management cycle¹. This showcases the benefits of making research data accessible at every stage of the research process, including intermediate findings.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

The deliverable is connected to several tasks of measure 6.3: distributed simulation for distributed energy systems (use case). First, it is connected to task 6.3.2, which is about self-healing flexibility aggregation. This is because the developed flexibility aggregation method is integrated into the scenario of this deliverable. The main focus of the deliverable is task 6.3.3, mechanisms for redispatch pools, as this task covers the base scenario for the deliverable. Additionally, this task is closely coupled with the integration of the communication network simulation in task 6.3.4. To sum up, the deliverable covers the following tasks.

- Task 6.3.2: Develop self-healing flexibility aggregation
- Task 6.3.3: Analyze mechanisms for redispatch pools
- Task 6.3.4: Conduct communication network simulation

¹original source: <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/learning-hub/research-data-management/>, similarly published on: <https://nfdi4energy.uol.de/>

Deliverable

The main topic of the deliverable is self-healing redispatch using distributed autonomous agents. Self-healing is defined as detecting, diagnosing, and repairing localized problems [7]. Therefore, it is essential to determine what kind of problems need to be detected and repaired. Section Incident Identification discusses how this is done, including the resulting research data from this step.

After identifying threats or potential problems, an agent-based application was chosen to investigate their impact on existing agent-based systems. Section Self-Healing Redispatch Scenario discusses the implementation of the application scenario, including the implementation of incidents and the investigation of their impacts. The detection of the incidents is essential for self-healing systems, and this topic, along with the corresponding research data, is discussed in section Anomaly Detection.

Incident Identification

Many different incidents endanger the functionality and reliability of energy systems, caused by environmental influences [8], cyber attacks [9], or component faults [10]. These incidents need to be investigated to be able to implement detection, location or even prevention mechanisms. There are different types, including disturbances, thefts, faults, threats, anomalies, intrusions, and attacks. Each type has different causes and effects.

Furthermore, all of these incidents have different methods of required action. A comparison regarding causes and effects is necessary to develop suitable detection methods for the specific faults. Taking into account the multiple facets of incidents is essential.

The Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG) is a research knowledge graph providing approaches for producing and (re-)using scientific knowledge from publications, software, and datasets [11]. As presented by Karras et al., the ORKG helps to organize scientific research and improve understanding and reuse [12]. Using the ORKG to organize our findings, we created a comparison of existing literature, considering incidents that endanger the reliability of energy systems. To organize and compare these approaches, the following categories are considered: cause, effect, goal, instance of, subcategories, and suggested action. The comparison can be used to select the most threatening incidents for a specific research area.

Research Data 1

The comparison of literature on incidents in energy systems that endanger functionality, reliability, and robustness can be found in the ORKG: <https://orkg.org/comparisons/R753752>.

The selection of the most relevant incidents regarding communication is discussed in a corresponding paper [6].

The described process for identifying relevant related work refers to the first step of the research data management cycle¹, as depicted in the following.

- Planning

For the planning phase, the identification of related work is essential. This was done by comparing existing approaches for the consideration of communication incidents according to literature research. Afterwards, the most suitable ones regarding communication in energy systems were identified. The publication of the comparison of related work facilitates the comprehension of the selection. It also enables the utilization and expansion of the outcomes.

Self-Healing Redispatch Scenario

To investigate the impact of potential problems or incidents, a baseline implementation of an example application was created. Here, a redispatch scenario was created and presented [6]. An agent system representing a neighborhood grid was introduced, managing Distributed Energy Resources (DER). The

agent system's task is self-consumption optimization, while additionally fulfilling redispatch requests from a grid operator.

To investigate the impact of potential threats, four different communication incidents were implemented and integrated into the scenario, based on the presented comparison of literature: asset failure, communication failure, communication delays and compromised process data [6]. For investigations of the selected incidents, 20 agents were considered, managing different types of DER. The behavior of the system with and without incidents happening was investigated, using metrics as message transmission duration, optimization duration, solution quality and number of exchanged messages [6].

Research Data 2

The implementation of the scenario, including the incidents, was made publicly available: <https://github.com/Digitalized-Energy-Systems/communication-incidents-in-cpes>. The implementation, incidents, and effects of incidents are discussed in a corresponding paper [6].

The scenario development covers the following steps of the research data management cycle¹.

- Production (collecting data) and analysis (processing and analyzing data)

By publishing the scenario itself, including integrated models, interfaces, etc., the scenario can easily be used and extended by other researchers. It also makes the work presented easier to understand.

Anomaly Detection

The next step in achieving self-healing even during incident occurrence is implementing detection methods, such as anomaly detection. For training effective anomaly detection techniques, detailed and realistic datasets are essential. These were created using the presented implementation of the redispatch scenario and the implemented incidents. First, normal operation data was collected. This data was used for the anomaly detection model to learn the system's behavior. Additionally, data containing incidents (anomalies) was collected to investigate the effectiveness of anomaly detection methods in identifying these incidents.

The resulting datasets were made publicly available, thus, these can be used to implement, compare and develop anomaly detection methods. A transformer autoencoder was implemented to perform anomaly detection using the described datasets[5]. Additionally, in order to make the results more comprehensible and reusable, the implemented anomaly detection models were also published. The datasets, models, and anomaly detection results are discussed in a corresponding paper [5].

Research Data 3

The datasets used for anomaly detection are publicly available: <https://zenodo.org/records/14333637>. Additionally, the implementation of the anomaly detection models were published: <https://gitlab.com/digitalized-energy-systems/models/detection-and-prediction-of-communication-incidents-in-cpes>.

Publishing the datasets and anomaly detection methods covers the following step of the research data management cycle¹.

- Storage and access (publishing and sharing data, preserving data)

The published datasets are easily reusable by others. These datasets enable the development of additional anomaly detection models and allow for the comparison of their performance with existing ones. Publishing the implemented models ensures traceability and reusability of the results. This ensures the persistence of the work.

The last step of the research data management cycle in energy system research¹ is the following:

- Re-use (re-using data)

By publishing individual steps along the research process rather than just the final results (e.g., anomaly detection results in a paper), there are far more opportunities for follow-up activities. Each of the individual points can be followed up on. This allows further incidents to be identified, integrated into the scenario or into other relevant scenarios, and further anomaly detection methods to be compared using the datasets. The implemented anomaly detection models can also be expanded.

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